

A Study of Various Sources Adopted by the Farmers for Earnings in Shiradhon Village

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Abstract:

Formers play vital role in the supply chain management. They people working very hard but they are not getting fair return on their work under the Shiradhon village lots of people comes under the marginal farming line because they are having below 2 hector farm land so they are unable to earn good from small place of land and because of that they are using multiple sources of earning to arrange their day-to-day expenses.

Keyword: Multiple sources of earnings farmers, Shiradhon Village.

Introduction:

Farmers are divided in 4 categories based on farm land. Following are this:

Category	Farm Land
Marginal Farmers	Less than 1 hectores
Small Farmers	1 To 2 hectores
Medium Farmer	2 To 10 hectores
Large Farmers	More than 10 hector

Large portion of farmers having below 10 hector land and because of small piece of land they fail to earn good amount. Due to less earning they are adopting more sources of income. Farmers doing farming or agricultural activity includes cultivation of crops (field horticultural fodder and plantation) as well as they are doing animal husbandry daring poultry Goat ship rearing in land fishing etc.

Literature Review:

In Rajasthan, small and marginal farmers face structural disadvantages that impact their ability to improve farm profitability. According to Chand et al. (2011), the profitability of farms less than two hectares is significantly lower due to limited access to credit, high input costs, and low

market prices for produce. These farmers often rely on traditional farming practices, resulting in lower yields compared to large-scale farms that benefit from modern technology and irrigation systems. The average yield per hectare for small farmers in Rajasthan is about 1.8 tonnes, compared to 3.4 tonnes for larger farms (Singh & Ahuja, 2013).

Ben whites (1997) in his article, " Agri-industry and contract farmers in the hilly southern region of unpaid west Java", covers two case studies, in both the studies contract farming communities deviate markedly from the neo populist vision of homogeneous, modernizing family farms and differentiation is quite marked and wage labor common. It concludes that institutional framework burdening contract farmers is in serious need of democratization on the problem is not one of formal structure in need of revision but of actual function and subsistence of relationship, which reflect the nature and exercise of power in rural society.

In Spain (Encisco et al., 1995), during the last decade, many farmers have moved from the traditional cereals or horticultural production towards diversification, combining traditional crops with livestock production. Farmers are thus making better use of resources, particularly labour and have often managed to increase their income to the extent that they are able to continue farming and remain in rural areas.

The relationship between income distribution and farm profitability has been widely studied, particularly within the context of developing economies like India. Small and marginal farmers, who constitute most of the agricultural workforce, often experience a disproportionate share of the economic challenges faced in rural areas. Several studies have explored the income disparity in agriculture, showing that farm size, access to resources, and market conditions are crucial determinants of profitability (Narayanamoorthy, 2006).

Research Methodology:

a. Research Design: For the purpose of study this research design is drafted and the steps to be taken for systematic research. With the help of present research design, we can easily understand the research process adopted for conducting this research.

b. Method Adopted: After reviewing various research methods, the researcher chose to carry out a survey, as the study aimed to collect information on attitudes, feelings, opinions, and perspectives—elements that are not easily observed directly.

c. Type of Research:

- 1) Descriptive in nature:
- 2) Qualitative technique:
- 3) Quantitative technique:

d. As per the nature of study researcher should collect data from various farmers from Shiradhon Village. For conducting this research, the researcher has used and relied on both primary and secondary sources of data collection.

Data Analysis:

Are research study shows that 100% of marginal small and medium scale farmers doing other activity with farming because they are getting insufficient amount from there small piece of land and for fulfilling their basic needs they are doing multilayer farming or adopting farming activity.

Interpretation: Here our research study shows that 100% farmers engaging with other activity along with farming for earning.

Here our research study accepted our first hypothesis that's those farmers using multiple sources of income.

Our research study shows that earning sources are classified into five categories:

Interpretation: Above chart shows that there is various sources of income are available for the farmers in that first is crop cultivation it includes actual farming second is multilayer farming here farmers cultivating seasonal product along with main product third one is livestock rearing it includes animal husbandry fourth one agricultural

labour here farmers working in others land and taking wages on it and last one is non-farm activity it includes small scale manufacturing dairy production shop keeping etc. Here our research study accepted second hypothesis that is farmers having multiple sources of earnings.

Interpretation: Here our research study shows that 100% farmers doing crop cultivation, 96% multilayer farming, 98% Livestock rearing, 64% agricultural labouring and 20% doing Non-agricultural activity

Here our research study accepted that other sources of income helps farmers to earn to increase their income.

Finding:

Our research study shows that marginal and small-scale farmers struggling a lot for fulfilling their basic needs due to having less income. So, they adopting other sources of income to increase their income

Conclusion:

Finaly I have conclude that farmers doing multiple work for arranging their bread and butter its difficult for them to get good return from there

small piece of land because of that they are adopting multiple sources of income.

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